

Reactivity of Chalkones : Action of Bromine and Ethyl Acetoacetate on 5'-Benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkones

Usha G. Joshi and G. C. Amin*

Action of bromine on 5'-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkones affords $\alpha\beta$ -dibromochalkone derivatives. With ethyl acetoacetate the same chalkones furnish ethyl 2-(substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylates, which undergo hydrolysis and simultaneous decarboxylation by aqueous ethanolic KOH to the corresponding substituted diphenylcyclohexanone derivatives.

Since a chalkone contains a double bond in the vicinity of the ketonic group, the action of bromine affords an interesting study. From the extensive work on the bromination of the chalkones, several empirical generalisations have been made (Tambor, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1704; Wheeler *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1320; 1939, 91, 93, 1004; Jadhav *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 28A, 125; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1948, 16, Part V, 43; 1954, 22, V, 43, *et seq*; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 746).

In the present investigation, 5'-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkones have been brominated by bromine in acetic acid solution. Although each chalkone molecule contains three benzene rings, only two bromine atoms are absorbed. Bromine atoms presumably enter only at the double bond, producing $\alpha\beta$ -dibromide (I), as proved by regeneration of the original chalkone by their elimination with KI in acetone solution. The reaction is smooth in all cases, unaffected by polybromination or other side reactions in spite of the presence of hydroxy and/or methoxy groups.

The action of ethyl acetoacetate on few chalkones has been reported by some workers (Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 730; 1902, 35, 395; Forster and Heilbron, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 340; Nadkarni *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1798; Davey and Gwilt, *ibid.*, 1957, 1015). In the present work, with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide, chalkones furnish ethyl 2-(substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylate (II: X = COOEt), even when free hydroxy and/or methoxy groups are present (Nadkarni *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The intermediate addition product could not, however, be isolated in any case. These diphenylcyclohexenone esters smoothly underwent hydrolysis and simultaneous decarboxylation by the action of aqueous ethanolic KOH, producing 2-(substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-ones (II: X = H). These cyclohexenone derivatives develop a red coloration with H_2SO_4 (conc.), indicative of the cyclohexanones of this type (Borsche, *Annalen*, 1910, 375, 145; Forster and Heilbron, *loc. cit.*).

* Present address : Research Laboratory, The Amar Dye Chem. Limited, P. B. 28, Kalyan, Bombay.

EXPERIMENTAL

5'-Benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkones were prepared by condensing 5-benzoyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone with appropriate benzaldehyde derivatives in presence of 40% KOH, as described earlier (Joshi and Amin, *Izvestia Akad. Nauk, USSR, Otdel. Khim. Nauk*, 1960, 267). Melting points of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

5'-Benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone $\alpha\beta$ -dibromides (I).

No.	*M.P.	Substituent	Cryst. appearance.	**M.P.	Formula	%Bromine	
						Found.	Calc.
1.	114°	Nil	Pale yellow shining needles (E)	185°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ Br ₂	32.45	32.78
2.	159°	2-Hydroxy	Yellow granules (E)	94°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ Br ₂	31.48	31.75
3.	153°	3-Hydroxy	Yellow granules (dil.A)	88°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ Br ₂	31.58	31.75
4.	194°	4-Hydroxy	Clusters of yellowish white needles (A)	82°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ Br ₂	31.63	31.75
5.	124°	4-Methoxy	Pale yellow granules (A)	161°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ Br ₂	30.56	30.89
6.	138°	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy	Yellow granules (A)	108°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₅ Br ₂	29.68	29.96
7.	185°	3, 4-Dimethoxy	Yellow short needles (dil.A)	107°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₆ Br ₂	28.93	29.19
8.	173°	3, 4-Methylenedioxy	Yellow short needles (dil.A)	165°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₅ Br ₂	29.83	30.07
9.	182°	3-Nitro	Buff-coloured short needles (dil.A)	110°	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ NBr ₂	29.82	30.02
10.	178°	3-Chloro-4-methoxy	Yellow granules (dil.A)	108°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ Br ₂ Cl	35.13 (Total halogen)	35.38

* Of the original chalkone.

** Of the dibromides.

The various $\alpha\beta$ -dibromochalkones (I), ethyl 2-(substituted phenyl)-4-(5'-benzoyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylates (II: X = COOEt) and the corresponding decarboethoxylated products (II: X = H) were prepared by the general methods described below. The compounds are listed in Table I—III. The solvent for crystallisation of each compound is indicated by letters in parenthesis (A, acetic acid, and E, ethanol) in the tables.

General Procedure

5'-Benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone $\alpha\beta$ -Dibromide (I).—5'-Benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) was treated with bromine in acetic acid (0.4 c.c., 50%). The reaction mixture was kept for 4 hours at room temperature (22-26°) and then diluted sufficiently with cold water. The yellow solid separating was filtered, washed with Na₂S₂O₃ solution (5%), and crystallised. In case of compounds No. 2, 3, 4, and 6, a dilute bromine solution in acetic acid (20-25%) was used.

Re-formation of the Original Chalkone by Debromination.—A mixture of the above dibromide (0.2 g.) and KI (0.2 g.) in dry acetone (20-25 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath at 65-70° for 2 to 3 hours. The solid, obtained after removal of acetone and pouring the contents in water, was washed with Na₂S₂O₃ solution (5%) and crystallised from ethanol. The product was identified as the original chalkone in each case by direct comparison with the authentic sample of the chalkone.

TABLE II

Ethyl 2-(substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylate
(II : X = COOEt).

No.	Substituent.	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
11	Nil	Pale yellow shining needles (E)	172°	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄	76.12	76.35	5.24	5.45
12	2'-Hydroxy	Slightly discoloured thin plates (E)	76°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅	73.28	73.67	5.03	5.26
13	3'-Hydroxy	Pale yellow granules (E)	152°	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄	73.38	73.67	5.02	5.26
14	4'-Hydroxy	Pale yellow short needles (E)	186°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₄	73.46	73.67	5.05	5.26
15	4'-Methoxy	Short pale yellow shining needles (E)	192°	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₄	73.80	74.04	5.31	5.53
16	3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxy	Long thick brownish needles (E)	77°	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₇	71.32	71.61	5.14	5.35
17	3',4'-Dimethoxy	Pale yellow short needles (E)	187°	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₇	71.72	71.99	5.39	5.60
18	3',4'-Methylene-dioxy	Pale yellow short needles (E)	188°	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₇	71.66	71.91	4.69	4.96
19	3'-Nitro	Shining short yellowish needles (E)	171°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₇ N	69.02	69.28	4.53	4.74
20	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxy	Short shining needles (E)	188°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 6.75	7.03		

TABLE III

2-(Substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one (II : X = H).

No.	Substituent.	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
21	Nil	Discolored white granules (E)	203°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₃	81.32	81.53	5.23	5.43
22	2'-Hydroxy	Pale yellow short needles (E)	215°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄	77.81	78.12	4.95	5.20
23	3'-Hydroxy	Light brown granules (E)	214°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	77.89	78.12	4.87	5.20
24	4'-Hydroxy	Pale yellow clusters of needles (E)	99°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	77.84	78.12	4.90	5.20
25	4'-Methoxy	White thin plates (E)	145°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	78.06	78.39	5.36	5.52
26	3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxy	Thin brownish plates (E)	155°	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₅	75.12	75.37	5.10	5.31
27	3',4'-Dimethoxy	Short white shining needles (E)	231°	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₅	75.42	75.70	5.37	5.60
28	3',4'-Methylene-dioxy	Brownish granules (E)	107°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₅	75.42	75.73	4.53	4.85
29	3'-Nitro	Yellowish thin plates (E)	185°	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ N	72.36	72.63	4.35	4.60
30	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxy	Pale yellow short needles (E)	214°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 7.99	8.20		

Ethyl 2-(Substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylate (II : X = —COOEt).—To a solution of sodium (0.2 g.) in absolute ethanol (15-20 c.c.) the chalkone (0.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.5 c.c.), followed by more ethanol (10 c.c.), were added. The coloured mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 to 3 hours and then diluted. On acidification by HCl (dil.), a yellow solid separated, which was crystallised from ethanol (E).

2-(Substituted phenyl)-4-(5''-benzoyl-2''-hydroxyphenyl)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one (II : X = H).—A solution of the above ethyl diphenylcyclohexenone carboxylate derivative (0.5 g.) in ethanol (15-20 c.c.) and 5% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) was refluxed on a boiling water bath for 5 to 6 hours. It was diluted with cold water (about 200 c.c.) and acidified by HCl. A brownish solid separating was collected, washed with 5% NaHCO₃ solution, and crystallised once or twice.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. N. COLLEGE,
VISNAGAR (GUJARAT STATE).

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